

Sargocentron_caudimaculatum -----
Sargocentron_spiniferum -----
Sargocentron_melanospilos -----AACCTCCA
Sargocentron_rubrum -----ACTCCA
Neoniphon_sammara -----TTATATAAT
Sargocentron_diadema -----
Sargocentron_punctatissimum -----
Neoniphon_opercularis -----ATCTACAACAACTATC
Myripristis_kuntee -----ACTTTTCAGACAT
Myripristis_violacea -----ATTTTCAGACAT
Myripristis_murdjan -----GTTCAACAGACAT
Myripristis_berndti -----TCCAACAGACAT
Myripristis_vittata -----TTTTTATACAT
Ostichthys_japonicus CTTCCAGAATAAATGCCACACATCTATTTATTAATGCGGTTGTAGACAT

Sargocentron_caudimaculatum -----AACTACG--CCAGCCAAA-TTAAGAGAAAACATACGAGTAACA
Sargocentron_spiniferum -----ACTACG--CCACACAAA-TTAAGAGAAAACATACGAGTGATA
Sargocentron_melanospilos AACAACCACACCG--ACACATAAAA-ATAAGGGCAAACACTCGAACACG
Sargocentron_rubrum AACAACCACACCG--ACACATAAAA-ATAAGGGCAAACACTCGAACACG
Neoniphon_sammara ATTATTTACCCCAATCTATAGCTAC-AAAAGAGAAAACCCCAAGCGACA
Sargocentron_diadema -----ACTTTAA-AAACCTCAA-CTTAAGGAAAAGCCTCGAGCGACA
Sargocentron_punctatissimum ---ATTTCCACGACCTTATCAAACCTAAAGGGAATTTCCCGACAATA
Neoniphon_opercularis TGTAATCTTTACACAATTTTATAGTTTGACGGGAAAAGTCCAAGTAGCG
Myripristis_kuntee ATATACAATATTACCACATACTG-TACTTAAAAACAATACACCCAATGTTT
Myripristis_violacea ATATACAATATTACCATATACTG-TACTTAAAAACAATACACCCAATGTTT
Myripristis_murdjan ATATATAATATTACCATATATTG-TACT-AAAACATTACATGTAATGCTC
Myripristis_berndti ATATACAATATTACCATATATTG-TACT-AAAACATTACATGTAATGCTC
Myripristis_vittata ATATACAATATCACCATATAATGATATCAAGTGCATTAATGTAATGCTT
Ostichthys_japonicus ATATGTATTATTACCATACATTTATATTAACATATAATATGTAATGCTT

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Sargocentron_caudimaculatum CGCA--ATGCTATGTATT--AACACCATTTCGT-CGGTACACACCATTTCAG
Sargocentron_spiniferum CGCA--ATGCTATGTATT--AACACCATTTCGT-CGGTACACACCATTTCAG
Sargocentron_melanospilos CCAAC-GCGCTATGTATT--TACACCATTAT-TGGTGTAAACCATACAG
Sargocentron_rubrum CCAAC-GCGCTATGTATT--TACACCATTAT-TGGTGTAAACCATACAA
Neoniphon_sammara ATAAC-TAACTATGTATT--TACACCATATAT-TGCTATACAATCCACAG
Sargocentron_diadema AC-AT-CCGCTATGTATTA-TACACCATATAT-TTATATTAACCATTTCAG
Sargocentron_punctatissimum AGATTTGAGCTATGTATT--ATCACCATACAA-TTATATTAACCATACAG
Neoniphon_opercularis AATAC-AACTATGTATT--TACACCATATAT-TGATATTAACCCACAG
Myripristis_kuntee TAAATACA-GTATATGTATTTACACCATATCA-TTATATTAACCATTCAA
Myripristis_violacea TAAATACA-GTATATGTATTTACACCATACCA-TTATATTAACCATTCAA
Myripristis_murdjan TCAAAACATACATATGTAATAACACCATAACGCTTATATTAACCACTCAG
Myripristis_berndti TTAAGACATACATATGTAATAACACCATAACATTTATATTAACCATTCAA
Myripristis_vittata ATAAACATAATATATGTTATTTACCATTAAA-TTATTTAACCATTCAA
Ostichthys_japonicus AAGGACA-AATATATGTATTATAACCATTGAT-TTATATTAACCATTCAA

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Sargocentron_caudimaculatum	GTAATACTA-----TCG-ACTAATATA--AATTTTACATAAACCATTA--
Sargocentron_spiniferum	GTAATACTA-----TCG-ACTAAATCA--AACTTTACATAAACCATTA--
Sargocentron_melanospilos	GTAATATTACAATATTC-ATGATTCCA--CATAGTACATTTTAAATTAC-
Sargocentron_rubrum	GTAATATTACAATATTC-ATGATTCCA--CATGGTACATTTTAAATTAC-
Neoniphon_sammara	GTAATACTAGTTAACTA-AATATATTT--CATAATACATTTATATTTACC
Sargocentron_diadema	GTAATACTAAATTATGATATAATTGTA--CATAAACCGTTATTGTAA--
Sargocentron_punctatissimum	GTAATACTAG-----TAAACCTTAAT--TATTTTACACACAAATACAT-
Neoniphon_opercularis	GTAATACTAATAAATATGCTTAATATTTGCATAATACATATTAATAATA
Myripristis_kuntee	GAAGTACA-TTAAATG-CTTAATTT-TACATAATACATTC-AAATCTT-
Myripristis_violacea	GAAATACA-TTAAATG-CTTAATTT-TACATAATACATTC-AAATCTT-
Myripristis_murdjan	GGAACAGA-TAGAAACG-CTTAATTT-CCCATAAGACATTTCAAGTCC-
Myripristis_berndti	GGAATGGAGTTAAAACG-CTTGATCTATCCATAAGACATTT-AAACTTT-
Myripristis_vittata	GGAATAAA-TGCGACCT-CATAATCT-TACATTATACATTA-ATACTCT-
Ostichthys_japonicus	GAAATAAC-AGTCAAGT-AA-AACAT-TACATAATACA--A-TTACATA-

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Sargocentron_caudimaculatum	AA-ATATAAAATATTGA-----ATTCTAAAGTAACGGGA---CCATA-T
Sargocentron_spiniferum	AA-ATATAAAATATTGA-----ATTCTAAAGTAACGAGA---CCATT-T
Sargocentron_melanospilos	AA-GTATGAAGACATAA-----AAATGATATCAAAGGAA---ATATGGT
Sargocentron_rubrum	AA-GTATGAAGACATAA-----GAATGGTATCAAAGGAA---ATATGGT
Neoniphon_sammara	GA-GAACGGGAACATAAC-----AAGTTAAATCAAGGAAATTTCCCTTAA
Sargocentron_diadema	AA-ATCCATAAATATCAT-----GAATTCAAGTGACGGGA---CCATA--
Sargocentron_punctatissimum	TG-GTTTAAATAGATCAC-----CATGCGAATAGTATGAA--AGTATGTT
Neoniphon_opercularis	AATATACATAAATAATTAATTACAGACTAACATTAAGATTATTTATGAG
Myripristis_kuntee	---TATTTTCATATATAAT-----CAATTCAAGGAA----TATAAT
Myripristis_violacea	---CATTTTCATATATAAT-----TAATTCAAGGAA----TATAGC
Myripristis_murdjan	---AGCCTCAGGCA-GATA-----CTGATTTAAGAGA----TA-AGT
Myripristis_berndti	---AGCTCCAGGCATGACA-----CTGATTTAAGAGA----TA-AGT
Myripristis_vittata	---TTATTCACCCCAGAT-----ACTCATCATC----CACTGT
Ostichthys_japonicus	---TTCATAACCATTTCGT-----AGTAA--AAT----AACTGT

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Sargocentron_caudimaculatum	ACTTGA-----AATATACA-----ACTAAAAAAA
Sargocentron_spiniferum	ACTTGA-----AATAACA-----ACTAAAAATA
Sargocentron_melanospilos	TCGTAA-----AATCAAGA-----CCTAGCATAA
Sargocentron_rubrum	TCGTAA-----AATCAAGA-----TCTAGCATAA
Neoniphon_sammara	AAGTAA-----GTTTAAGA-----CCGAGCTATT
Sargocentron_diadema	---TAT-----AATAAAAT-----TTTAACAGAT
Sargocentron_punctatissimum	TGAAAG-----ATTTAAGA-----CCGAACACAT
Neoniphon_opercularis	TCTTAACCAATATACAAGTATTTAATAGACATATATTATTTCTACTGAAT
Myripristis_kuntee	ACTAGT-----AAACTCCACA-----CCTAACATAA
Myripristis_violacea	ACTAGT-----AAACTCCACA-----CTTAACATAA
Myripristis_murdjan	ACCAGA-----ACACA--AGA-----CCTAACAGGA
Myripristis_berndti	ACTATA-----AAATA--AGA-----CCTAACAAATG
Myripristis_vittata	ATACAC-----GGATTTAAGA-----CCTAACACA-
Ostichthys_japonicus	AACCAA-----AAATTTAAGA-----CCTAACACTT

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Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

TGAAATCA--AATGGCAG--ATATACCAAGTAAT-CACCATTACAAGTGA
TGAAATCA--AATAGCAG--ATATACCAAGTAAC-CACCATTACAAGTGA
AGAAATCAT-GGCCAAAG--ATATACCAAGTCCC-CACCATATTA--TGA
AGAAATCAT-GGCCAAAG--ATATACCAAGTCCC-CACCATACCTA--TGA
CAAACCTTATAAGATAAAG--ATATACCAAGTCCC-CAACATCTCGTCATA
T-ATATCATCAGTCA-AG--ATATACCAAGTAAT-CCACATCCTGTTATA
TTAATTCATCAGTTT-AG--ATATACCAAGTAAT-CAACATTCCTATAATA
TGAACCTACAAGTAACAAGAACGTACCAAGTAACTCAACATCCCCTTATG
AAGTTATTTTAAAC--CAG--ATATACCAAGTAAT-CACCATTCATTTC
CAATTATTTTAAAC--CAG--ATATACCAAGTAAC-CACCATTCCTATTC
AGAAGAAATCGATTGCAC--ATATACCAAGTACT-CAACAATCTATTT-A
GAAAGAAATCGATTGCAT--ATATACCAAGCACT-CAACAACCTATTT-A
ATATTCATTAGTC--AAG--ATATACCAAGCACC-CAACATCCGGCC---
AAACCCATTAGTC--AAG--ATATACCACGTACC-CACCATCCCCTT---

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Myripristis_violacea
Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

AAATCACAT--TTTTAATGTAGTAAGAAACCACCAAAG-AATGATTACTA
AAATCGCACCATATTAATGTAGTAAGAAACCACCAAAG-AATGATTACTA
GATTAAAGGAATCTTAATGTAGTAAGAGACCACCAAAG-AATGATTCTTA
GATTGAAGGAATCTTAATGTAGTAAGAGACCACCAAAG-AATGATTCTTA
AAATT-CAGAACCTTTAATGTAGTAAGAAACCACCAAAG-TTTGATTCCTG
AAACTTAACTAT-TTAATGTAGTAAGAAACCACCAAAG-ATTGATTCCTT
TCTCTACAATAT-TTAATGTAGTAAGAAATCACCACCAAAG-TTTGATTCCTT
GATTT--AGAATCTTAATGTAGTAAGAAATCACCACCAAAG-TTTGATTCCTA
AGATCAAAAT-C-TGGATGCAGTAAGAAACCACCAAAG-GGTGATTCCTG
AGATCAAAAT-C-TGGATGCAGTAAGAAACCACCAAAG-GGTGATTCCTA
GAATAAGAATAT-TTAATGTAGTAAGAAACCAGCAATC-GGTGATTCCTG
AAATAAGAATAT-TTAATGTAGTAAGAAACCAGCAATC-GGTGATTCCTC
AAGAACAATAT-TTAATGTAGTAAGAAACCACCAAAG-GGTGATTCCTA
GAACACAAATTT-TTAATGTAGTAAGAAACCACCAAAG-GGTGATTCCTA

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Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

AATGCATTATA-TTCTTGATGGTCAGGGACAA-TAGAC-TGTGGGGGTA-
AATGCATTGTA-TTCTTGATGGTCAGGGACAA-TAGAC-TGTGGGGGTA-
AATGCATACGG-TTCTTGATGGTCAGGGACAA-TA-AT-TGTGGGGGTT-
AATGTACACGG-TTCTTGATGGTCAGGGACAA-TA-AT-TGTGGGGGTT-
AATGCATGCGAGTTAATGATGGTCAAGGACAAATAAAA-TGTGGGGGTA-
AATGCATACTA-TTATTGATGGTCAGGGACAA-TAACA-TGTGAGGGTT-
AATGCATATTA-TTCGTGATAGTCAAGGACA--TCAAT-CGTGAGGGTA-
AATGCATATGCTTTAATGATAATCAAGGGCAAGCACT-AACAAGAATTT
AAGGTACTCGG-TTCTTGATAGTCAAGGGCAGGCAAGCATGTGGGGGTA-
AAGATACTCGG-TTCTTGATGGTCAAGGGCAGGCAAGCATGTGGGGGTA-
AATGTATATCA-ATCATGATAATCACGGACAATAAAC--CGTGGGGGTA-
AATGTATATCA-ATCATGATAATCACGGACAATAAAC--TGTGGGGGTA-
AATGTATCTAG-TCCTTGATGGTCAGGGACAGTAATC---GTGGGGGTT-
ATTGCATACGG-TTCTTGATGGTCAAGGGACAGAAATTT---GTGGGGGTT-

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Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

GCC-AAAGGGCAGTTGGTTCTCCTTTTTTAGCTTCCTTTCACCTTACATT
GCT-AAGGGGCAGTTGGTTTTCTTTTTTAGCTTCCTTTCACCTTACATC
TCT-AAGGGGCAACGGGTTTTCTTTTT-AGCTTCCTTTCACCTTACATT
TCT-AAGGGGCAACGGGTTTTCTTTTT-AGCTTCCTTTCACCTTACATC
TCT-AAGGGACAATTGGTTAATCTTTTTTAGCTTCCTTTCATTTTACATC
TCCCGAGGGGCAAGGGGTTTTCTTTTT-AGCTTCCTTTCACCTTACATC
TCC-AAAGGGCAATTGGTATTCTTTTTTAGCTTCCTTTCACCTTACATT
TCC-AAAGGACAATGGGTTTATAATTTTTAGCTTCCTTTCACCTTGACATC
TCT-AAAGGGTAAGGGGTTTTACCTTTTCCGCTCCCTTTCATTTTACATT
TCT-AAAGGGTAAGGGGTTTTACTTTTTCCGCTCCCTTTCATTTTACATT
TCT-AAAGGGTAAGGGGTTTTACCTTTTTTCCGCTCCCTTTCATTTTACATC
TCT-AAAGGGTAAGGGGTTTTACCTTTTTTCCGCTCCCTTTCATTTTACATC
TCT-AAAGGGCAACGGGTTTTACCTTTTTTCCGCTCCCTTTCATTTTACATC
TCT-AAAGGGCAAGGGGTTCTTTTTTAGCTTCCTTTCATTTTACATC
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Myripristis_violacea
Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

CCGGTGCA--ACGGCAAA-TAACTTAATGAAGGTTGAACATAC-TTTATG
CCAGTGCA--ACGATAAAATAACTGAATGAAGGTTGAACATATATTTATA
CCGGTGCG--GCGGCAGA-AGGTAAACTCAAGGTTGAACAT---TTTCT-
CCGGTGCA--GCGGCAGA-AGGTAAACTCAAGGTTGAACAT---TTTCT-
CCCGTGCATAACGAAAACATTTCAAAGTGAAGGTAGAACAT---TTCCT-
CCGGTGCA--ATGTCAATAATTAATAAT-AAGGTTGAACATAT-TATCTG
CCGGTGCG--AAGGATAAAATGATGATTTAAGGTAGTTTCAATA--TCCT-
CCAGTGCAAAAGCTAAGACAAACGTAAGTTAAGGTTGAACATT--TACCT-
CCGGTGCA---CCC-TAAAAATGAAAGCCAAGGTAGAACATA--TTCCT-
CCGGTGCA---CCC-TAAAAATGAAAGTCAAGGTAGAACATA--TTCCT-
CCGGTGCA---AAG-AAAAATTTAAT-TGGAGGTAGAACATG--TTCCT-
CCAGTGCA---AAG-GAAGGACTGAA-TGGAAGTAGAACATG--TTCCT-
CCAGTGCA---GCGCTAAGGATAAAAATCAAGGTAGAGCATT--TCCTT-
CCAGTGCA---GCGCTAAGGTTAACTAATAAGGTAGAACATT--TTCTT-
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Myripristis_violacea
Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

TTGATATAATAACAAGTAATGTATTCTCCGGGCAGGAATATG----CATG
ATGGTGTAAATAACAATAATGTTTTCCCGGGCAA-AATGTG----CATG
-----TGCTTGCAAGGAAATAGTATT----CATG
-----TGCTTGCAAGGAAATAGTATT----CATG
-----TGTATTCGGGAGGTAATGGTGGTA-T-CATG
-----GTGTAAATAAAGAAATA-TGTAT-T-CATG
-----TGCCAGAGTTAATGATAGTA-TTCATG
-----TGCATTCGTAAAACGTAAAACAATAATTCATG
-----TGTAACATAAGATACACTTTT----AATG
-----TGTAACACAAGACACACTTTT----AATG
-----TGCT-CGCGTAAAAATATGTTT----AGTG
-----TGCC-CGCATAAA-TACGTTT----AATG
-----GCACGCACAGGAAATATTATT----CGTG
-----GCTCGCA-AGCGAATAGTATT----CATG
**

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Myripristis_violacea
Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

-GTGTTAAAACCTTATA----TAATCAA-TGAAACCACAAATAGGGATATC
-GTGTTAAAACCTTATA----TCATTAA-TGAATCCACAAATAAGGATATC
-GTGGTTAGATTTA-----TTATTAA-AGAA-CCACATTATTAGATATC
-GTGGTTAGATTTA-----TCGTAA-AGAA-CCACATTATTAGATATC
TATGAGAAGGTTTGTA---CAATTAA-TGATCCACATATTTAGATATC
-GTGGAAGATTTG-----TTTTTAA-GAAT--TACATATTAAGATATC
-ATGATAAACTATT-----CACCAA-ATAA-CCACATATTAGGATATC
TTAATAAAGGCTTAAAATAATCATTAA-CAAACCACATATTAAGATATC
-GAGTAAAGGATGGAA-----AGTAAT--ATCTCACATAAAGTAATATC
-GAGTAAAGATGGAA-----AGTAAT--ATCTGCATAAAGTGATATC
-GAGGGAAGACTAGAA-----GGAAAGTAGAGTTTGCATGTAATGGATTC
-GAGGTAGGCTGAAA-----GAAAAGCAAGACTTGCATGTAATGGATTC
-GAGGTAAAGATTTATA-----AATGAA--AAATCCACATAAATATTTTC
-GTGGAAGATTTT-----AATTAA--ATAACCACATATTAGGATATC

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Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

AAGTGCATAAGTAATTTTT-TACCTCGAGCAATTTACCCAATAATATTG
AAGTGCATAAATAATTTTT-TACCTCGAGCAATTTACCCAATAATATTG
AAGTGCATAATAATTTTT-TTTTCTAGGCAAAT--ACCTAATA-TATCG
AAGTGCATAATAATTTTT-TTTTCTAGGCAAAT--ACCTAATA-TATCG
AAGTGCATAAT--ATTTTT-TTTTCTAGACAAT--ATTCTATGATATTT
AAGGACATAAATAACTTTTATTAAGTAGGCATAT--ATCTAATA-TATGA
AAGTGCATAACATATTTCT--TTACTAGGCAAAT--ATCCAACA-TATCA
AAGTGCATAACAATTTTTTATTTCTAGGCAAAT--ATCCTATA-TATCA
AAGTGCATAATATATTTTATTTCTCAATAGGCAAAG--CTCTAACA-CACCA
AAGTGCATAATATATTT-TTATTACTAGGCAAAA--CTCTAACA-CACCA
AAGTGCATAATATATTT-TTACTACCAGGCAAAA--CTCTAACA-CACCA
ATGTGCATAATACTTTTATTTCTCGACAAAT--CCCTA-TA-TATCA
ATGTGCATAATAT-TTTTTATTTTCTAGGCAAAT--ACCTAATA-TATTA

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Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

CCCCCTTCGTTTTTGCGCGTTAAACCCCC-TACCCCC-AACACCCTA
CCCCCTCCGTTTTTGCGCGTTAAACCCCC-TACCCCC-AACACCCTA
CCCC-TCCGTTTTTGCGCGTTAAACCCCC-TACCCCCCTAACACTCCTG
CCCC-TCCGTTTTTGCGCGTTAAACCCCC-TACCCCCCTAACACTCCTA
CCCC-CTGGTTTTTGCGCGTTAAACCCCC-TACCCCC-AATACTCCTG
CCCCCTCGTTTTTGCGCGT-AAACCCCC-TACCCCC-AATACTCCTG
CCCC-CTGGTTTTTGCGCGT-AAACCCCC-TACCCCC-AACACTCCTG
CCCC-CTGGTTTTTGCGCGTTAAACCCCC-TACCCCC-TACTCCTG
CCCC-CTGGTTTTTGCGCGTTAAACCCCC-TACCCCC-TACTCCTG
CCCC-CTGGTTTTTGCGCGTTAAACCCCCCTACTCCTG
CCCC-CTGGTTTTTGCGCGTTAAACCCCCCTACTCCTG
CCCC-CTGGTTTTTGCGCGT-AAACCCCC-TACCCCC-TACTCCTG
CCCC-TCGGTTTTTGCGCGTCAAACCCCC-TACCCCC-TACTCCTG

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Neoniphon_opercularis
Myripristis_kuntee
Myripristis_violacea
Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

AGATCTCTATCACTCCTGTAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGATAAACCTTCGGG
AGATCTCTATCACTCCTGTAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGATAAACCTTCGGG
AGATCTATATTATTCTGTAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGA--AAACCTCGAG
AGATCTATATTATTCTGTAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGA--AAACCTCGAG
AGATTCTAATATTCTGTAAACCCCC-GAAAAACAGGACTAAACCTCGAG
AGATTACTATTATTCTGTAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGATCTAACCCCGAG
AGATCGTATTATTCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAC--AACCTCGAG
AGATCACTGTCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCC-GAAAAACAGGACTAAACCTCGAG
AGACCTCTATCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAC-AAATCTCAAA
AGACCTCTATCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAC-AAATCTCAAA
AGATCCTTATCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAC-AAACCTCAAA
AGATCCTTATCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAC-AAACCTCAAA
AGACCTCTATCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAA-AAGTCTCAAA
AGATCTTTTACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAA-A-GTCTCAAG
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Sargocentron_melanospilos
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Sargocentron_diadema
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Myripristis_violacea
Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

CATTG-----CTACTTCCCATCAAATTTGCGTCTATCACAAT----
CATTG-----CTACTTCAACATCAAATTTGCGTCTATCACAAT----
TGTTA-----ATTATCCTCCCT--AATTTATGTCTATTACAAT----
TGTTA-----ATTATCCTCCCT--AATTTATGTCTATTACAAT----
TATTA-----ACCTATTTTAAATTCAAATTTATATTTACTTAAATTGTA
TATTA-----AATATCCCAGCATAAAATTTATGCTTATTATATT---
TGTTATA-----AGCCTCCCTAATCTAAATTACTCATTTTACATT---
TACTAAT-----TCACTCCAATTCAAAAATAT-TTTACTTATATT---
CAGTGTCTTAAATATTTCCAACCACATTTATTTGTGCTTATTTACATT---
CAGTGTCTTATACTCCAACCACATTTATTTGTGCTTATTTACATT---
CAGTGTCTTATAATCTTCTAACCACATTTATTTGTGCTTATTTACATT---
TAGTGTCTATT--TTTTTTAACCACATCTATTTATGCTTATTTACATT---
TGATA-----TTTAAGTAATTCAATTTATGTATATTTACATT---
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Sargocentron_spiniferum
Sargocentron_melanospilos
Sargocentron_rubrum
Neoniphon_sammara
Sargocentron_diadema
Sargocentron_punctatissimum
Neoniphon_opercularis
Myripristis_kuntee
Myripristis_violacea
Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

---ATTTCAATATTG-CACATTTG-----
---ATTTCAATATTG-CACATTTT-----
---ATTTCAATATTA-CACATTTG-----
---ATTTCAATATTA-CACATTTT-----
ATAATTACAATATTAACCTATTTTAAATTCAAATTTATATTTWCTTWAATTG
---ATTATAATATTG-CACATAG-----
---ATTATAATATTG-CACATGG-----
---ATTACAGTATTGCAGCATTACAGTACTACAACATTTTTTATAATG--
---ATTATAATATTA-CACACAG-----
---ATTATAATATTA-CACACAG-----
---ATTATAATATTA-CACACAG-----
---ATTATAATATTA-CACACA-----
---ATTATAATATTA-CACACA-----
---ATTATAATATTG-CACACA-----
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Sargocentron_caudimaculatum
Sargocentron_spiniferum
Sargocentron_melanospilos
Sargocentron_rubrum
Neoniphon_sammara
Sargocentron_diadema
Sargocentron_punctatissimum
Neoniphon_opercularis
Myripristis_kuntee
Myripristis_violacea
Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

AGATCTCTATCACTCCTGTAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGATAAACCTTCGGG
AGATCTCTATCACTCCTGTAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGATAAACCTTCGGG
AGATCTATATTATTCTGTAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGA--AAACCTCGAG
AGATCTATATTATTCTGTAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGA--AAACCTCGAG
AGATTCTAATATTCTGTAAACCCCC-GAAACAGGACTAAACCTCGAG
AGATTACTATTATTCTGTAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGATCTAACCCCGAG
AGATCGTATTATTCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAC--AACCTCGAG
AGATCACTGTCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCC-GAAACAGGACTAAACCTCGAG
AGACCTCTATCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAC-AAATCTCAAA
AGACCTCTATCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAC-AAACCTCAAA
AGATCCTTATCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAC-AAACCTCAAA
AGATCCTTATCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAC-AAACCTCAAA
AGACCTCTATCACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAA-AAGTCTCAAA
AGATCTTTTACTCCTGTCAAACCCCCCGGAAACAGGAA-A-GTCTCAAG
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Sargocentron_caudimaculatum
Sargocentron_spiniferum
Sargocentron_melanospilos
Sargocentron_rubrum
Neoniphon_sammara
Sargocentron_diadema
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Neoniphon_opercularis
Myripristis_kuntee
Myripristis_violacea
Myripristis_murdjan
Myripristis_berndti
Myripristis_vittata
Ostichthys_japonicus

CATTG-----CTACTTCCCATCAAATTTGCGTCTATCACAAT----
CATTG-----CTACTTCAACATCAAATTTGCGTCTATCACAAT----
TGTTA-----ATTATCCTCCCT--AATTTATGTCTATTACAAT----
TGTTA-----ATTATCCTCCCT--AATTTATGTCTATTACAAT----
TATTA-----ACCTATTTTAATTCAAATTTATATTACTTAAATTGTA
TATTA-----AATATCCCAGCATAAAATTTATGCTTATTATATT---
TGTTATA-----AGCCTCCCTAATCTAAATTACTCATTTTACATT---
TACTAAT-----TCACTCCAATTCAAAAATAT-TTTACTTATATT---
CAGTGTCTTAAATATTTCCAACCACATTTATTTGTGCTTATTTACATT---
CAGTGTCTTATACTCCAACCACATTTATTTGTGCTTATTTACATT---
CAGTGTCTTAAATCTTCTAACCACATTTATTTGTGCTTATTTACATT---
TAGTGTCTATT--TTTTTTAACCACATCTATTTATGCTTATTTACATT---
TGATA-----TTTAAGTAATTCAATTTATGTATATTTACATT---
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Sargocentron_caudimaculatum
Sargocentron_spiniferum
Sargocentron_melanospilos
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---ATTTCAATATTG-CACATTTG-----
---ATTTCAATATTG-CACATTTT-----
---ATTTCAATATTA-CACATTTG-----
---ATTTCAATATTA-CACATTTT-----
ATAATTACAATATTAACCTATTTAATTCAAATTTATATTTWCTTWAATTG
---ATTATAATATTG-CACATAG-----
---ATTATAATATTG-CACATGG-----
---ATTACAGTATTGCAGCATTACAGTACTACAACATTTTTTATAATG--
---ATTATAATATTA-CACACAG-----
---ATTATAATATTA-CACACAG-----
---ATTATAATATTA-CACACAG-----
---ATTATAATATTA-CACACA-----
---ATTATAATATTA-CACACA-----
---ATTATAATATTG-CACACA-----
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Sargocentron_caudimaculatum	-----
Sargocentron_spiniiferum	-----
Sargocentron_melanospilos	-----
Sargocentron_rubrum	-----
Neoniphon_sammara	TTCACATA
Sargocentron_diadema	-----
Sargocentron_punctatissimum	-----
Neoniphon_opercularis	-----
Myripristis_kuntee	-----
Myripristis_violacea	-----
Myripristis_murdjan	-----
Myripristis_berndti	-----
Myripristis_vittata	-----
Ostichthys_japonicus	-----